

CLASSIFICATION OF LAKE EYRE LANGUAGES

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1. Introduction¹

The genetic classification of Australian Aboriginal languages has been a topic of heated debate among linguists over the past thirty years. The first attempt at a comprehensive classification for the whole continent was that proposed by O'Grady, Voegelin and Voegelin 1966 (see also O'Grady, Wurm and Hale 1966) using the lexicostatistical method. This classification claimed that all Australian languages were members of a single phylum and that there were twenty nine "phylic families" represented on the continent. One of these, Pama-Nyungan, covers the southern eight-tenths of the continent. A revised version of the classification was published by Wurm (1972) who reduced the number of families to twenty six (see also Wurm and Hattori 1982).

Over the past ten years these classifications has been increasingly subjected to scrutiny. Dixon (1980:262ft) voiced strong criticism of the lexicostatistical classifications and claimed to have established a genetic classification (using traditional comparative-historical techniques) whereby all Australian languages, with the exception of Tiwi and Djingili, form a single genetic family and derive from a single ancestor proto-Australian (pA) (Dixon 1980:225). He argues that the distinction between Pama-Nyungan (PN) and non-Pama-Nyungan (nonPN) proposed by O'Grady, Hale and Wurm is not genetic but a typological and areal one. He says that "should not be inferred that PN is in any sense a genetic unity - that there was a proto-PN, as an early descendant of pA" (Dixon 1980:236).

Dixon's views have been challenged by Blake (1989, 1990) who compared verb pronominal prefix forms in a range of non-Pama-Nyungan languages and has been able to argue for reconstructing a prom-Northern system from which the attested nonPN systems evolve. According to Blake's proposal, PN and nonPN are genetic labels. Evidence from lexical comparisons presented in Evans 1989 supports Blake's position. Dixon (p.c. 1988) has accepted the arguments put forward by Blake and Evans and now agrees that Pama-Nyungan is a valid genetic label.

While this work on higher level groupings has been a major focus of research and discussion, there have been relatively few published studies of lower level subgroups within Pama-Nyungan languages. The exceptions are Austin (1981, 1988) who considers the Kanyara and Mantharta languages of Western Australia, Black (1980) the Norman-Pama subgroup of Paman (see also Hale 1976), and Evans (1985) the Tangkic languages of the Gulf of Carpentaria. It is remarkable that little progress to date has been made in "bottom-up" language comparison and the delineation of detailed subgrouping within PN.

This paper is an attempt to classify genetically the languages traditionally spoken in the region around Lake Eyre (northern South Australia) and to reconstruct the ancestor languages from which they descend. I will argue that a close genetic relationship can be demonstrated for the languages spoken to the east of Lake Eyre, and that these languages are more distantly related to Pitta-Pitta of central-western Queensland and Wangkumarra of south-western Queensland (into a grouping that can be called "Karnic"). I will propose a set of

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reconstructions for three levels of the Karnic group. I then examine data on languages spoken to the west of Lake Eyre (Wangkangurru and Arabana) and argue that, contrary to suggestions by Breen and Hercus, these languages are not particularly closely related to the eastern Lake Eyre languages and that shared cognates are either due to local borrowing or to common inheritance from a more distant ancestor, probably at a time depth close to Pama-Nyungan. This paper is thus an exercise in detailed genetic reconstruction and subgrouping for a local geographical region of Australia. Hopefully, further studies will illuminate other higher level groupings between the reconstructions proposed here and Pama-Nyungan itself.

2. The Lake Eyre Languages

The region around Lake Eyre was traditionally one of some linguistic diversity. The following is a list of the ten languages (and sources of data on them) from the east of Lake Eyre considered in this study:

1. Thirrari (abbreviated as Ti) - spoken on the southern and eastern shores of Lake Eyre. Data sources are Austin 1974-77, 1981, Reuther 1981, MS;
2. Diyari (Di) - spoken east of Thirrari along the lower reaches of Cooper Creek. Sources are Austin 1974-77, 1981, Reuther 1981, MS;
3. Ngamini (Ng) - spoken north of Diyari along the lower Diamantina River. Sources are Breen 1971, Breen 1976a, Austin in prep, Reuther 1981, MS (Reuther's data is indicated as NgR in the discussion below);
4. Karangura (Kn) - spoken north of Ngamini along the Diamantina River to Birdsville. The meagre data on this language is fully examined in Austin (in press);
5. Yarluyadi (Yl) - spoken north of Karangura to the Mulligan River in western Queensland. Data comes from fieldnotes and tapes collected by Austin and Breen (see also Austin (in prep));
6. Mithaka (Mi) - spoken east of Yarluyadi in south-west Queensland. There is very little data on this language - see Breen 1971, 1976a (also Austin's transcriptions of Breen's Mithaka fieldtapes);
7. Karuwali (Ka) - traditionally spoken north and east of Mithaka. There is no contemporary data on this language and only two old written sources: Curr 1886, W.H.W. 1912;
8. Yawarrawarrka (Yw) - spoken east of Karangura and Ngamini in the extreme north-east of South Australia. Data on this language comes from Breen 1971. The Yawarrawarrka recorded by Reuther 1981, MS is a slightly different dialect than that recorded by Breen. It is indicated as YwR in the following;
9. Yandruwandha (Ya) - spoken south of Yawarrawarrka and east of Diyari. There is a large amount of data on this language collected primarily by Breen - see Breen 1971, 1975, 1976b, 1981, 1990, and Kerwin and Breen 1981, 1986. Data on slightly different dialects of Yandruwandha was collected by Wurm 1957, and Reuther 1981, MS (indicated as YaR below);
10. Pirlatapa (N) - spoken south of Yandruwandha and east of Diyari. The slight amount of data on this language has been thoroughly examined in Austin 1990.

To the north and west of Lake Eyre were spoken Arabana (Ar) and Wangkangurru (Wn). These are shown to be closely related languages by Hercus 1990. Other sources of data are O'Grady and Klokeid 1968-69, and Reuther 1981, MS.

South of Lake Eyre were a number of languages that appear to be closely related. I have considered data on the following:

1. Adnyamathanha (Ad) - spoken in the northern Flinders Ranges. Data comes from Coulthard and Schebeck 1987, Schebeck 1987, O'Grady 1967;
2. Pankarla (Pa) - spoken south and west of Adnyamathanha. There is a brief vocabulary in Hale 1960;
3. Nugunu (Nu) - spoken south of Pankarla near Port Augusta. Data comes from O'Grady 1958/60;
4. Narangga (Na) - spoken south of Pankarla. Data comes from O'Grady 1958.

Two groups of more distant languages are considered in this study. To the north of the eastern Lake Eyre languages lie the Pitta-Pitta group (abbreviated Pp); these have been described by Blake 1979b (see also Breen 1971). East of the eastern Lake Eyre languages is the Wangkumarra group (abbreviated Wm). Data on these languages comes from Breen (n.d.) (see also Breen 1971, and Robertson 1984, 1985).

Using the available data I have attempted to classify the languages of the Lake Eyre region and to establish reconstructions of putative ancestor languages.

3. Previous classifications of Lake Eyre Languages

O'Grady, Voegelin and Voegelin 1966 and Wurm 1972 classify the eastern Lake Eyre languages as members of the "Dieric Group" of Pama-Nyungan. This group is divided further into three subgroups, the "Karna Subgroup", the "Ngura Subgroup" and the "Yalyi Subgroup". Other languages of the region are classified into the Arabanic, Mitakudic and Pitta-Pittic Groups of Pama-Nyungan.

The internal classification of the Dieric Group is given by Wurm (1972:132-3) as follows:²

Karna Subgroup

1. Dieri - Tirari - Jandruwanta - Ngameni - Karangura - Yelyendi
2. Pilatapa
3. Jauaraworka (Jawaraworka)
4. Karendala — Kungadutji (Gungadidji) — Kulumali — Bidia — Murulta — Karuwali

Ngura Subgroup

1. Punthamara — Ngandangara — Kalali (Garlali) — Bitjara? — Tereila? (Diraila?) — Wangkumara — Ngurawola
2. Badjiri (Badjara, Baddjeri)

Yalyi Subgroup

Nadikali - Malyangapa

Breen 1971 is a major restudy of western Queensland languages using a large amount of newly collected data not available to previous researchers. The classification is primarily lexico-statistically based and Breen modifies the classification of O'Grady et al, setting up a "Karnic Group" which (Breen 1971:21):

"comprises four subgroups: the Narla Sub-Group is the former Arabanic Group; the Palku Sub-Group is the former Pitta-Pittic Group; the Kama Sub-Group comprises the former Karna Sub-Group of Dieric, plus Mithaka, minus Bidia

² The spelling of language names in Wurm 1972 is retained here.

(Birria), Kungatutji, Kulumali and Karendala; the Ngura Sub-Group is the former Ngura Sub-Group plus Karendala.”

As evidence of the relationship between members of this Karnic Group, Breen (1971:29) provides partial cognate counts for comparisons of languages across the group. The figures are in the range 20%-40% (if we ignore neighbouring languages where cognate counts could be artificially increased by borrowing), with a low of 19% (for Palku-Ngura subgroups) and a high of 48% (Karna-Palku, represented by Yarluyandi-Pitta-Pitta). A sample of the figures given is:

Karnic Group: Cognate Counts (from Breen 1971)

Wangkangurru

27	Yandrruwandha			
40		Yarluyandi		
35		48	Pitta-Pitta	
31		20	Punthamarra	

Breen also proposes an internal classification of the Karna Sub-Group as follows (Breen 1971:24):

“both the old and new data justify the grouping of Jandruwanta and Jawarawarka as dialects of the same language, and Dieri, Ngamani, and Jeluyendi as belonging to a different language.”

This gives the Karna Sub-Group consisting of three distinct languages:

1. Diyari - Ngamani - Yarluyandi
2. Mithaka - Karuwali
3. Yandrruwandha - Yawarrawarrka

Lexicostatistical figures of percentage cognates to support this classification are presented in a table (Breen 1971:22) which may be rearranged as follows:³

Yandrruwandha

75	Yawarrawarrka				
36	36	Karuwali			
47	53	74	Mithaka		
67	67	50	75	Yarluyandi	
49	51	31	46	74	Ngamani
56					73 Diyari

Breen (1971:23) points to phonological and morphological similarities that appear to agree with the lexical classification:

“morphological similarities between languages in this sub-group provide supporting evidence for this classification; in particular, they have in common the use of auxiliaries to form certain verb tenses or aspects ... In addition, they share a phonological phenomenon unusual in Australian languages: a contrast between voiced and voiceless stops, probably confined to apical stops”

³ Breen (personal communication) points out some typographical errors in the original table which are corrected here.

Breen’s classification of the Lake Eyre region languages has been essentially repeated in several publications by Hercus, most recently in Hercus 1989 where she provides a diagram (page 150) “sketch of the genetic relationships between the languages of the Lake Eyre basin and neighbouring areas”. This is given below.

Hercus (1989:150) also argues, however, that alongside these genetic relationships, there has been “diffusion of a grammatical structure”, an affix marking actions performed for the benefit of someone other than the subject, (see also Hercus 1987) and that:

“[t]hese similarities were not regular in any way, sometimes features appear to have crossed from one subgroup or even group to another. Other features were limited in their overall geographical extension: there was no overall pattern, no single focal point, but probably a series of areas where linguistic diffusion took place”.

(Hercus 1989:150)

In connection with this apparent evidence of linguistic diffusion, she notes (Hercus 1989:151):

“doubt at least part of the reason for the complex network of linguistic diffusion was that the population of the whole area was linked by a network of similar social structures ... There were also strong links in trade and exchange (McBryde 1987) as well as mythological and ritual associations.”

If this is correct, then we must be careful to distinguish between features due to borrowing and diffusion and those due to genetic inheritance in assigning languages to classifications.

4. Methodology of this study

My approach has been to follow one of the traditional methodologies of historical linguistics, namely ‘backwards reconstruction’ (see Hock 1986:581ff, Anttila 1972:229ff). Firstly, we propose a subgrouping of languages and then reconstruct intermediate parent proto-languages on the basis of comparisons of the languages believed to subgroup together. Data from immediate daughter languages only is taken into consideration at each level of

reconstruction.⁴ The subgrouping I have adopted places all the eastern Lake Eyre languages, plus Wangkumarra and Pitta-Pitta in a single genetic group (Karnic); the eastern Lake Eyre languages are further grouped into Central Karnic and Western Karnic. The subgrouping is summarised as follows (for language name abbreviations see 3 above):

The reconstructed proto-languages are thus:

1. proto-Western Karnic (pWK) - daughter languages are Diyari, Ngamini, Yarluyandi;
2. proto-Central Karnic (pCK) - daughter languages are pWK, Yandrruwandha, Yawarrawarrka, Karuwali and Mithaka;
3. proto-Karnic (pK) - daughter languages are pCK, Pitta-Pitta and Wangkumarra.

Notice that I do not subgroup Arabana and Wangkangurru with the Karnic languages (see further 6 below).

Using the data currently available I am able to propose 374 reconstructions; 46 for proto Western Karnic, 160 for proto-Central Karnic and 168 for proto-Karnic. The reconstructions are detailed in Appendix 1. In a few instances it has been necessary to reconstruct doublets, that is a pair of ancestral forms that are both reflected in the daughter languages. These are also discussed in Appendix 1. There is a finderlist of all the reconstructions in Appendix 2.

5. Classification of Lake Eyre languages

The strongest evidence for the genetic relationship of the Karnic languages comes from comparison of the personal pronoun paradigms. Not only are there sets of forms reconstructable, but also there are developments which seem to be unique to Karnic and that differentiate it as a subgroup of Pama-Nyungan. These innovations are:

1. **ngali* as first person dual exclusive, inclusive, as in other Pama-Nyungan languages (see Dixon 1980);
2. development of a gender contrast in third person singular pronouns. We can reconstruct: 3sg masculine **nhawu*, 3sg feminine **nhani*;

⁴ My method was to create a database using DBASE III software, firstly of vocabulary from languages in the lowest level subgroup and to reconstruct their ancestor (pWK in this case). I then added columns to the database for the next level, stored the vocabulary data, and then reconstructed for that level (pCK). At each level, only data from immediate daughter languages (including proto-languages) was considered

in the singular second and third persons, presence of a distinctive *k* in the dative/purposive paradigm. It seems that this *k* has been introduced into the 1sg paradigm in central Karnic by analogy with the 2sg and 3sg forms: cf.

	<u>1sg nom</u>	<u>1sg erg</u>	<u>1sg acc</u>	<u>1sg dat/purp</u>
Di	<i>nganhi</i>	<i>ngathu</i>	<i>nganha</i>	<i>ngakarni</i>
Ng	<i>nganyi</i>	<i>ngathi</i>	<i>nganha</i>	<i>ngakarni</i>
Ya	<i>nganyi</i>	<i>ngathu</i>	<i>nganha</i>	<i>ngakarni</i>
Pp	<i>ngantja</i>	<i>ngathu</i>	<i>nganya</i>	<i>nganyari</i>
Wm	<i>nganyi</i>	<i>ngathu</i>	<i>nganha</i>	<i>ngantja(ni)</i>
	<u>2sg nom</u>	<u>2sg erg</u>	<u>2sg acc</u>	<u>2sg dat/purp</u>
Di	<i>yini</i>	<i>yundrru</i>	<i>yinanha</i>	<i>yingkarni</i>
Ng	<i>yini</i>	<i>yindi</i>	<i>yinanha</i>	<i>yingkarni</i>
Ya	<i>yini</i>	<i>yundrru</i>	<i>yina</i>	<i>yinggani</i>
Pp	<i>yinpa</i>	<i>yintu</i>	<i>yina</i>	<i>yinkari</i>
Wm	<i>yini</i>	<i>yundrru</i>	<i>yina</i>	<i>yinkani</i>
	<u>3sgm nom</u>	<u>3sgm erg</u>	<u>3sgm acc</u>	<u>3sgm dat/purp</u>
Di	<i>nhawu</i>	<i>nhulu</i>	<i>nhinha</i>	<i>nhungkarni</i>
Ng	<i>nhapa</i>	<i>nhulpa</i>	<i>nhinha</i>	<i>nhungkarni</i>
Ya	<i>nhunu</i>	<i>n/zulu</i>	<i>yinha</i>	<i>nhunggani</i>
Pp	<i>nhuwa</i>	<i>n/zulu</i>	<i>yinha</i>	<i>nhukari</i>
Wm	<i>nhiya</i>	<i>nhulu</i>	<i>nhinha</i>	<i>nhungka(ni)</i>
	<u>3sgf nom</u>	<u>3sgf erg</u>	<u>3sgf acc</u>	<u>3sgf dat/purp</u>
Di	<i>nizani</i>	<i>nhandrru</i>	<i>nhanha</i>	<i>nhangkarni</i>
Ng	<i>nhanpa</i>	<i>nhandu</i>	<i>nhanha</i>	<i>nhangkarni</i>
Ya	<i>nhani</i>	<i>nhandrru</i>	<i>nhanha</i>	<i>nhanggani</i>
Pp	<i>nhanpa</i>	<i>nhantu</i>	<i>nhana</i>	<i>nhankari</i>
Wm	<i>nhani</i>	<i>nhandrru</i>	<i>nhanha</i>	<i>nhangka(ni)</i>

These are the clearest evidence of genetic affiliation.

Pronoun comparisons are also supported by reflexes of Pama-Nyungan case suffixes. In Karnic languages the dative/purposive case form (*-ngka* or *-nga*) reflects an old Pama-Nyungan LOCATIVE **-ngka* (see Dixon 1980). Note that a locative case form is NOT reconstructable for Karnic, since each daughter language has a different form for that case affix. Central Karnic is also marked by an innovation in the ergative case marker, namely the descent of **-lu* as *-li*.

	<u>erg</u>	<u>acc</u>	<u>dat/purp</u>	<u>loc</u>
Di ⁵	-(ya)li/-ndrru	-nha	-ya/-rni/-nhangka	-nhi
Ng ⁶	-li/-nu	-nha	-ngka	-mu
Ya	-u	-nha	-ngarri	-yi
Pp	-lu	-nha	-nga	-ina
Wm ⁷	-lu/-ndrru	-nha	-nga	-langa

Comparative grammatical studies in Karnic are at an early stage, but it is likely that further research will point to other grammatical similarities that support the lexical reconstructions.

5.1. Subgrouping

There is some lexical evidence to support the subgrouping of Western Karnic languages, in the form of lexical innovations. The following five reconstructions show replacements from proto Karnic into proto-Western Karnic, ie. local innovations. The forms are:

<u>proto-Western Karnic</u>	<u>proto-Karnic</u>	<u>Gloss</u>
*ngayani	*ngandrra	‘1plincl nom’
*ngayaninha	*ngandrranha	‘1plincl acc’
*maru	*tjimpa	‘black’
*nganthi	*kathi	‘meat’
*pira	*nyangi	‘moon’

Central Karnic provides no evidence for such innovation.

5.2. Proto-Karnic phonology

The reconstructed phonological system of Karnic shows six points of articulation for stops and nasals. There also appears to be a voicing contrast reconstructable for apico-alveolar stops (in consonant clusters only). In Central Karnic a voicing contrast for both apico-alveolar and apico-dental positions is reconstructable. Both proto languages have four laterals, two semi-vowels and three ‘r-sounds’: flap (*rr), trill (*rrh), and retroflex continuant (*r). There are just three vowels to be reconstructed. The consonant systems are set out in the following table:

⁵ The various forms of the Diyari ergative are distributed as follows: -(ya)li after singular common nouns, -li after non-singular common nouns and masculine names, and -ndrru after feminine names. For the dative we have: -ya after singular common nouns, -rni after non-singular common nouns and masculine names, and -nhangka after feminine names.

⁶ The forms of the Ngamini ergative are: -li after non-singular common nouns, and -nu after singular common nouns (apparently a reduction from *-ndu — Yarluyandi has -ndu in this context).

⁷ Forms of the Wangkumarra ergative are: -lu after masculine singular nouns, -ndrru after feminine singular and plural nouns.

	<u>Bilabial</u>	<u>Laming-dental</u>	<u>Apico-alveolar</u>	<u>Lamino-palatal</u>	<u>Apico-domal</u>	<u>Dorso-velar</u>
Stop - vcless	<i>p</i>	<i>th</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>tj</i>	<i>rt</i>	<i>k</i>
(-vcd			<i>d</i>		<i>rd</i>)
Nasal	<i>m</i>	<i>nh</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>ny</i>	<i>rn</i>	<i>ng</i>
Lateral		<i>lh</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>ly</i>	<i>rl</i>	
Semi-vowel	<i>w</i>			<i>y</i>		
Flap			<i>rr</i>			
Trill			<i>rrh</i>			
Continuant					<i>r</i>	

The presence of a voicing contrast in proto-Karnic is interesting since this is an unusual feature of Australian languages. It seems, however, that a contrast for apico-alveolars following *l is attested, as the following near minimal pair shows:

pK **kalta* ‘blue-tongue lizard’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Wm: *kalta*

pK **ngalda* ‘ldlincl nom’ Di, Ya, Yw: *ngalrra*; Wm: *ngala*; Ng, Yl: *ngalku*

Following *n only *t is found — this descends as *d* or *drr* in Central Karnic and Wangkumarra. A contrast between this voiced sound and voiceless *t is reconstructable for proto-Central Karnic, as exemplified in:

pCK **kantu* ‘rock wallaby’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya: *kantu*

pCK **kundrrukundrru* ‘cough’ Di, Ng, Ya, YwR: *kundrrukundrru*

A contrast for apico-domals in intervocalic position is also reconstructable in Central Karnic. Consider the following cognate sets:

*rt

**karta* ‘boom’ Di, YaR, YwR: *karta*

**warta* ‘butt, trunk’ Di, Ya: *warta*; Ng: *kardi*

**yartu* ‘sated’ Di, Ya: *yartu*

**warnta* ‘short’ Ya, Wm: *warnta*; Di, Ng: *wardu*; Yl, Mi: *wartu*

*rd

**kardi* ‘sister’s husband’ Di, NgR: *kardi*; YaR, YwR: *kardrri*

**marda* ‘stone’ Di, Ng: *marda*; Yl: *marta*; Ya, Yw, Mi, Ka: *mardrra*

**mardi* ‘heavy’ Di, Ng: *mardi*; Ya: *mardrri*

**mardu* ‘taste’ Di, Ng, Ya, Yw: *mardu*

**parda-* ‘to hold’ Di, Ng: *parda-*; Yl, Pp: *parta-*; Ya, Mi, Ka: *pardrra-*

**parndi-* ‘to hit’ Yl: *parndi-*; Ya, Yw, Mi, Wm: *parndrri-*

Yandruwandha, Yawarrawarrka and Wangkumarra also have contrastive voiced stops at other points of articulation (see Breen 1975, n.d.). However reconstruction suggests that voiced stops (other than apicals) arose in these languages following a nasal (homorganic or non homorganic) as the second member of a consonant cluster WHEN THE WORD-INITIAL CONSONANT IN THE PROTO LANGUAGE WAS A NASAL. When the reconstructed form begins with a non-nasal consonant then voiceless stops occur in the Yandruwandha, Yawarrawarrka

and Wangkumarra⁸ reflexes. Examples of this are the following which show descent of *k as voiced g and *tj as voiced dj and *th as dh:

1. *k --> g
 - pK *mingka ‘hole’ Ya, Mi: *mingga*; Di, Ng, Yl, Pp: *mingka*
 - pK *ngarnka ‘beard’ Yl, Ya: *ngarn.ga*; Di, Ng, Ka: *ngarnka*; Wm, Pp: *nganka*
 - pK *nhangkarni ‘3sgfem dat/purp’ Di, Ng, Yl: *nhangkarni*; Ya: *nhanggani*; Wm: *nhangka(ni)*; Pp: *nhankari*
 - pK *nhungkarni ‘3sgmasc dat/purp’ Di, Ng, Yl: *nhungkarni*; Wm: *nhungka(ni)*; Ya: *nhunggani*; Yw: *nhungkunu*; Ka: *nhukarni*; Pp: *nhukari*
 - pCK *mankarrha ‘girl’ Di, Ng: *mankarrha*; Ya: *man.garrhi*; Yw: *man.garrha*
 - pCK *nhingki ‘here’ Ya: *nhinggi*; Di: *nhingki*
2. *tj -- > dj
 - pK *ngantja- *yura ‘to want’ Di, Ng: *ngantja-*; Wm: *ngandja-*; Yl, Ya: *yura-*; Mi: *yuri*
3. *th -- > dh
 - pCK *nhintha ‘shame’ Ya: *ninda*; Di, Ng, Yl: *nhintha*

Compare these with reflexes containing voiceless stops:

 - pK *kungku ‘head’ Yl, Mi, Ka: *kungku*; Ya, Yw: *kungka*; Wm: *kuka*
 - pK *kunkj ‘doctor’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya: *kunki*; Wm: *kunki* ‘ghost’
 - pK *thungka ‘rotten’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Mi, Wm: *thungka*; Yw: *thungwa*
 - pK *yunka- ‘sulky’ Di, Ya, Wm *yunka*; Pp *yunku-* ‘to sulk’
 - pCK *tarnka- ‘to find’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, YwR: *darnk-*
 - pCK *turnka- ‘to emerge’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya: *durnka-*
 - pCK *kingka- ‘to laugh’ Di, Ng, Yl: *kingka-*; Ya: *yingka-*; Mi: *kingki-*
 - pCK *pangki ‘rib’ Yw: *pangki*; Di, Ya: *pangkithirri*
 - pCK *purnka- ‘to grow’ Di, Ng, Ya: *purnka-*
5. *tj.-- >tj
 - pCK *pantja ‘knee’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw: *pantja*
6. *th --> th
 - pCK *tanthu ‘soft’ Di, Ya, YwR: *danthu*
 - pCK *kantha ‘grass’ Di, NgR, Yl, Ya, YwR: *kantha*
 - pCK *thinthipirri ‘elbow’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw: *thinthipirri*
 - pK *kjintha ‘shrimp’ Di, Ng, Ya: *kintha*; Pp: *kintharlu*; Wm: *thintha*

It is probable that the enlarged voicing contrast that is seen currently in these languages results from the spread of the voiced stops out of this environment.⁹

⁸ There seem to be some unexplained exceptions in the Wangkumarra data which need clarification. Note that in the transcription I use *n.g* for a sequence of apical nasal followed by a voiced velar stop, in contrast to *ng* for the velar nasal consonant.

⁹ There are two problematic cognate sets for this account, namely proto-Karnic **kanku* ‘boy’ reflected in Wangkumarra unexpectedly as *kan.gu*, and proto-Central Karnic **yinpa.* ‘to send’ reflected in Yandruwandha as *yinba-*. Notice also Yandruwandha *yinggani* 2sg dative, but the medial voiced stop here could be due to analogical pressure from elsewhere in the pronoun paradigms (since other pronouns begin with nasals).

5.3. Changes in the Central Karnic daughter languages

In the descent from proto-Central Karnic we can identify a number of changes that have taken place in individual languages. These are detailed as follows:

1. in Ngamini final *u-* in verbs corresponds to *a-* in the other Central Karnic languages when the verb contains a *u* in the next to last syllable. It seems that Ngamini has undergone a type of limited vowel harmony. Note that these verbs do not take the present tense suffix *-yi*; the bare root is used for present tense function. Examples are:¹⁰

<u>Ngamini</u>	<u>Divan</u>	<u>Yan/Yaw</u>	<u>Gloss</u>
<i>kumu</i> [R]	<i>kuma</i>	<i>kuma</i> [R]	'to dance (of women)'
<i>kurnpu</i> [R]	<i>kurnpa</i>	<i>kurnpa</i> [R]	'to caress'
<i>kurrhu</i>	<i>kurrha</i>	<i>kurrha</i>	'to put'
<i>kurdu</i>	<i>kurda</i>		'to fall (of rain)'
<i>maranguku</i> [R]	<i>maranguka</i>	<i>maranguka</i> [R]	'to help'
<i>murdu</i> [R]	<i>murda</i>	<i>murda</i> [R]	'to stop'
<i>pupu</i> [R]	<i>pupa</i>	<i>pupa</i> [R]	'to admonish'
<i>purru</i> [R]	<i>purra</i>	<i>purra</i> [R]	'to wade'
<i>nyurlku</i>		<i>nyurlka</i>	'to lose'
<i>yupu</i> [R]	<i>yupa</i>	<i>yupa</i> [R]	'to annoy'
<i>yurku</i>	<i>yurka</i>	<i>yutja</i>	'to swallow'

2. in Yawarrawarrka clusters of lateral plus peripheral stops *p* and *k* are changed as follows:

- (a) retroflex lateral+*p* becomes stop+*p* (all my examples are from Reuther and it is impossible to tell if the resulting stop is retroflex)
- (b) lateral+*k* becomes stop+*k* in the dialect recorded by Breen, and become *tj* in the dialect recorded by Reuther.¹¹

Examples of these changes are:

(a)

<u>Yawarrawarrka</u>	<u>Yandruwandha</u>	<u>Ngamini</u>	<u>Divan</u>	<u>Gloss</u>
<i>patpa</i> [R]	<i>parlpa</i>			'language, tongue'
<i>pitpa</i> [R]	<i>pirlpa</i>	<i>pirlpa</i>	<i>pirlpa</i>	'eyebrow'
<i>witpa</i> [R]		<i>wirpa</i>	<i>wirlpa</i>	'hole'
<i>witpi</i> [R]		<i>wirpi</i>	<i>wirpi</i>	'to whistle'

Compare these with words containing an apical lateral plus stop cluster, such as Yawarrawarrka *kilpa* [R] 'to despise' and *ngalpa* [R] 'lap'.

¹⁰ The symbol [R] indicates that the form is recorded in Reuther MS and not in materials recorded by Austin and/or Breen.

¹¹ Breen collected a few words from Ben Kerwin of a language he called "Matja". In this data the word for 'know' is represented as *kitja-*. It may be that Reuther's Yawarrawarrka and "Matja" are the same.

(b)¹²

<u>Yawarra [R]</u>	<u>Yawarra</u>	<u>Yandmi</u>	<u>Ngamini</u>	<u>Diyari</u>	<u>Gloss</u>
<i>kitja</i>	<i>kitka</i>	<i>kilka</i>			'to know'
<i>witja</i>		<i>wilka</i> [R]			'to pull out'
<i>mitji</i>	<i>mitji</i>	<i>mitji</i>	<i>mirki</i>	<i>milki</i>	'eye'
<i>matja</i>		<i>malka</i>	<i>malka</i>	<i>malka</i>	'mark'
<i>yutja</i>		<i>yurlka</i>	<i>yurku</i>	<i>yurlka</i>	'to swallow'

Notice that in the Yawarrawarrka recorded by Reuther there is a merger of ancestral **lk* with *tj*. Thus *matja* [R] 'long ago' (pK **matja*) and *ngatji* [R] 'to beg, pray' (pCK **ngatjj-*).

3. in Yandrruwandha final *a* becomes *i* after *rrh*. Examples are:

<u>Yandrruwandha</u>	<u>Yawarrawarrka</u>	<u>Ngamini</u>	<u>Divan</u>	<u>Gloss</u>
<i>man.garrhi</i>	<i>man.garrha</i>		<i>mankarrha</i>	'girl'
<i>kaparrhi</i>	<i>kaparrha</i> [R]	<i>kaparrha</i>	<i>kaparrha</i>	'root'

4. in Yandrruwandha initial *tj* before *i* and *a* becomes *y*, while before *u* it remains as *tj*. Examples are:

<u>Yandrruwandha</u>	<u>Yawarrawarrka</u>	<u>Gloss</u>
<i>yarrha</i>	<i>tjarrha</i>	'boomerang'
<i>yiwa</i>	<i>tjiwara</i>	'woman'
<i>yimpa</i>	<i>tjimpa</i>	'black'

cf.

<i>tjukurrhu</i>	<i>tjukurrhu</i>	'kangaroo'
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6. The position of Arabana and Wangkangurru

As noted above, Hercus proposes a close genetic relationship between Arabana-Wangkangurru and Karnic, and classifies them as a subgroup of Karnic. The reasons she has put forward for this classification include lexical and morphological similarities. Unfortunately, neither of these seems to stand up to close inspection.

An example of a morphological similarity proposed by Hercus (in Hercus 1989) is the presence of a stem-forming affix that marks action carried out for a beneficiary other than the subject. Thus Arabana-Wangkangurru has *paka-* 'to dig', *paka-la-* 'to dig for someone', Pitta Pitta *marri-* 'to get', *marri-la-* 'to get for someone', Diyari *nandrra-* 'to hit', *nandrripa-* 'to hit for someone', Ngamini *nhirrka-* 'to look', *nhirrka-pa-* 'to look for someone', Yandrruwandha *wawa-* 'to look', *wawa-na-* 'to look for someone'. However, the presence of this affix is an areal feature not a genetic one. In Karnic proper the relevant affix (formally Di *-ipa*, Ng *-pa*, Ya *-na*, Pp *-la*) additionally turns certain intransitive verb roots into causative transitive stems, eg. Diyari *yirrtji-* 'to arise' *yirrtjipa-* 'to make rise', *tharrka-* 'to stand' *tharrkipa-* 'to make stand'. In Arabana-Wangkangurru the corresponding benefactive affix DOES NOT have a causativising function; this instead is marked by change of stem final *a* to *i*.

Perhaps the strongest evidence against subgrouping of Arabana-Wangkangurru with Karnic comes from the two areas we identified as pointers to genetic connection within Karnic, namely pronouns and case forms. Arabana and Wangkangurru do not reflect the pronouns we

¹² There are some apparent exceptions in Reuther's Yawarrawarrka, namely *nyurlka-* [R] 'to lose', *kalka* [R] 'evening', and *karlku* [R] 'rushes'.

have reconstructed for Karnic, especially: (a) the characteristic *k* in dative/purposive forms, and (b) the masculine/feminine distinction in 3sg (Arabana-Wangkangurru only have 3sg *uka*). Consider the following examples:

	proto-Karnic	Arabana	Wangkangurru
1dlincl	* <i>ngalta</i>	<i>arrinpa</i>	<i>arruna</i>
1plexcl	* <i>ngana</i>	<i>arni</i>	<i>arni</i>

For the cases, Arabana-Wangkangurru do not reflect Karnic innovations from Pama-Nyungan, viz. ergative as *-li/-ntu* (Ar-Wk have *-ru*), and dative *-ngka* (Ar-Wk have Pama-Nyungan *-ku*, they reflect Pama-Nyungan locative as *-nga*, from **-ngka/*

When considering lexical similarities, it is important to compare Arabana-Wangkangurru with RECONSTRUCTED forms at each of the three levels we have identified. Close examination shows that there are only nine forms cognate with pWK and all could be loans (one also has a cognate in Adnyamathanha, to the south, and is probably a loan in that language). The relevant forms are:

- pWK **kaka* ‘mother’s brother’ Wn: *kaka*, Ar: *kakaka*
- pWK **kumarrhi* ‘blood’ Wn, Ar: *kubmarrhi* [Ad *umarrhi* ‘blood’]
- pWK **kunankarri* ‘south’ Wn, Ar: *kudnankarri*
- pWK **mani* ‘to get’ Wn, Ar: *mani*
- pWK **pantu* ‘lake’ Wn, Ar: *pantu*
- pWK **ptji* ‘bark’ Wn, Ar: *pitjimurrhu*
- pWK **tharra* ‘thigh’ Wn, Ar: *tharra*
- pWK **wana* ‘yamstick’ Wn, Ar: *wana* [Ba *wana* ‘boomerang’ Hercus 1982:298, Ad, Nu *wadna* ‘boomerang’]
- pWK **yantakarra* ‘west’ Wn, Ar: *yantakarra*

There are thirteen Arabana-Wangkangurru words with cognates in pCK (and two have cognates in Ad and languages to south). These are:

- pCK **taka-* ‘to pierce’ Wn, Ar: *thaka-*
- pCK **malhantji* ‘bad’ Wn, Ar: *madlanthi*
- pCK **mankarrha* ‘girl’ Wn: *mankarrha* [Ad *mankarrha* ‘big girl, young woman’]
- pCK **mardu* ‘taste’ Wn: *martu*
- pCK **marna* ‘mouth’ Wn, Ar: *marna*
- pCK **marrka-* ‘to crawl’ Wn, Ar: *marrka-*
- pCK **milki* ‘eye’ Wn: *milikarti*, Ar: *miltjaardi*
- pCK **ngara* ‘heart’ Ar: *ngara*
- pCK **pangki* ‘rib’ Wn, Ar: *pangki*
- pCK **pantja* ‘knee’ Wn: *pantjakarti*, Ar: *pantjaarti*
- pCK **pirrhi* ‘fingernail’ Wn: *pirrhi*, Ar: *nyirrhi* [Ad *virrhi* ‘claw, nail (of finger or toe)’, Nu *pirrinyji* ‘fingernail’]
- pCK **wakarrha* ‘nape’ Ar: *wakarrha*
- pCK **yartu* ‘sated’ Wn, Ar: *yartu*

The remaining similarities are cognates with proto-Karnic reconstructions; almost all of these have cognates in languages to the south and east, as far away as Baagandji on the Darling

River, reflecting no doubt a local vocabulary that goes back to Pama-Nyungan (or some ancestor close to Pama-Nyungan). Consider the following:

- pK **kaku* ‘elder sister’ Wn, Ar: *kaku*
- pK **kalhu* ‘liver’ Ar: *kalyu*
- pK **kanti* ‘spinifex wax’ Wn, Ar: *kanti*
- pK **kanyini* ‘mother’s mother’ Wn, Ar: *kadhini* [Ad *adnyani* ‘mother’s mother’]
- pK **karrhawarra* ‘eaglehawk’ Wn: *karrhawara*
- pK **karrka*.. ‘to call out’ Wn, Ar: *karrka*- [Ba *karrka*- ‘to cry out, scream’ Hercus (1982:285)]
- pK **kathi* ‘meat’ Wn: *kathi* [cf. Kungkari, Birria *kathi* ‘meat’ Breen 1971:57)]
- pK **kirra* ‘boomerang’ Wn, Ar: *kirra*
- pK **kuku* ‘back’ Wn, Ar: *kuku* [cf. Ba *kuku* ‘end’ Hercus (1982:287)]
- pK **kuna* ‘faeces’ Wn, Ar: *kudna* [cf. Ba *kuna* ‘faeces, bowel’ Hercus (1982:288), Ad *urdna* ‘faeces’, Nu *kudna* ‘excrement’]
- pK **maka* ‘fire’ Wn, Ar: *maka*
- pK **makamaka* ‘hot’ Wn, Ar: *makamaka*
- pK **malka* ‘mark’ Wn, Ar: *malka* [cf. Ad *malka* ‘mark’]
- pK **mara* ‘hand’ Wn, Ar: *mara* [cf. Ba *mara* ‘hand’ Hercus (1982:291), Ad, Nu, Pa *mara* ‘hand’]
- pK **marni* ‘fat’ Ar: *marni* [cf. Ba *marni* ‘fat’ Hercus (1982:290), Ad, Nu *marni* ‘fat, grease’, Pa *marni* ‘fat’]
- pK **mingka* ‘hole’ Wn, Ar: *mingka* [cf. Ba *mingka* ‘hole’ Hercus (1982:291)]
- pK **minha* ‘what’ Wn, Ar: *minha* [cf. Ba *minha* ‘what’ Hercus (1982:291)]
- pK **mirrtja* ‘noise’ Wn, Ar: *irrtja* [cf. Ad *itjii*- ‘to be noisy, make noise’]
- pK **mulha* ‘nose’ Wn, Ar: *midla* [cf. Ad *mudla* ‘nose’, Na, Nu, Pa *mudlha* ‘nose’]
- pK **ngaltja* ‘saliva’ Wn, Ar: *ngaltja* [cf. Ba *ngaltja* ‘spit, phlegm’ Hercus (1982:295), Ad *ngaltja* ‘spittle, beer’]
- pK **ngama* ‘breast’ Wn, Ar: *ngama* [cf. Ba *ngama* ‘breast, milk’ Hercus (1982:295), Ad *ngama* ‘breast, milk’, Pa *ngama* ‘breast’]
- pK **nganha* ‘1sg acc’ Wn, Ar: *anha*
- pK **ngapiri* ‘father’ Ar: *apitji*
- pK **ngarnka* ‘beard’ Wn: *ngarnka* [cf. Ad, Nu, Pa *ngarnka* ‘beard’]
- pK **ngathu* ‘1sg erg’ Wn, Ar: *athu*
- pK **ngunku* ‘chewing tobacco’ Wn, Ar: *ngunku*
- pK **ngurra* ‘camp’ Wn, Ar: *ngurra*
- pK **nhampa* ‘to bury’ Wn: *nhampa*
- pK **nhupa* ‘spouse’ Wn, Ar: *nhupa*
- pK **paku*- ‘to dig’ Wn, Ar: *paka*- [Ad *vaku*- ‘to build, construct’]
- pK **pampu* ‘egg’ Wn, Ar: *papu*
- pK **pani* ‘none’ Wn: *padni*
- pK **paratji* ‘light’ Wn: *paratji* , Ar: *paru*
- pK **parta* ‘to hold’ Wn, Ar: *parta*

- pK **parrkulu* ‘two’ Wn, Ar: *parrkulu* [cf. Ba *parrkulu* ‘two’ Hercus (1982:276)]
- pK **parru* ‘yellow ochre’ Wn: *parru*
- pK **pilpa* ‘eyebrow’ Wn: *pilpa*
- pK **pinti* ‘grasshopper’ Wn: *pintiltja* [cf. Ba *piinti* ‘grasshopper’ Hercus (1982:277)]
- pK **pitjirrhi* ‘pitchere’ Wn: *pitjirrhi*
- pK **pula* ‘3dl nom’ Wn, Ar: *pula*
- pK **pulanha* ‘3dl acc’ Wn, Ar: *pulanha*
- pK **tharli* ‘tongue’ Wn, Ar: *tharli* [Ba *tharlinya* ‘tongue’ Hercus (1982:280), Ad, Nu *yarli* ‘tongue’, Pa *tjarliny* ‘tongue’]
- pK **tharrka-* ‘to stand’ Wn, Ar: *tharrka-* [cf. Ba *thaarri-* ‘to stand’ Hercus (1982:281)]
- pK **thika-* ‘to return’ Wn, Ar: *thika-* [cf. Ba *thika-* ‘to return’ Hercus (1982:281), Ad *ika* ‘to sit’, Nu *thika-* ‘sit’, Pa *ikatha* ‘sit’]
- pK **thina* ‘foot’ Wn, Ar: *thidna* [cf. Ba *thina* ‘foot’ Hercus (1982:281), Ad, Pa *idna* ‘foot’, Na, Nu *thidna* ‘foot’]
- pK **thirriwa* ‘east’ Wn, Ar: *thirriwa* [cf. Kalkatungu *thirriwa* ‘south’ Blake (1979c: 194)]
- pK **thupu* ‘smoke’ Wn, Ar: *thupu*
- pK **wama* ‘carpet snake’ Wn, Ar: *wabma* [Nu, Pa *wabma* ‘snake’]
- pK **wangka* ‘to sing’ Wn, Ar: *wangka-* [Ad *wangka-* ‘to say, speak, talk’, Nu *wangkaja* ‘speak’, Pa *wangkatha* ‘speak’]
- pK **wani* ‘corroboree’ Wn, Ar: *wadni*
- pK **wara* ‘who’ Wn, Ar: *wara* [cf. Kungkari, Birria *wara* ‘who’ Breen (197 1:61)]
- pK **warrhukatji* ‘emu’ Wn: *warrhukathi* [cf. Ad *warrhatji* ‘emu’, Nu *warriti* ‘emu’]
- pK **yuntu* ‘2sg erg’ Wn: *untu*, Ar: *antu*
- pK **yurlku.* ‘to swallow’ Wn, Ar: *yurlka-*

For these reasons I do not believe that Arabana and Wangkangurru are to be grouped into the same immediate genetic grouping as Karnic, although it is clear that they are related at a more distant level.

7. Conclusions

In this paper we have presented a series of arguments about the classification of Lake Eyre languages and suggested that all the eastern Lake Eyre languages belong to a Karnic subgroup. This is further subgrouped into Central Karnic and Western Karnic. Several hundred reconstructions supporting this analysis are given and a number of changes in the daughter languages, including development of a voicing contrast for stops, are traced.

It is likely that further research will see the refinement and modification of the reconstructions presented here, but this paper can serve as a first step towards the establishment of a lower level grouping of the Pama-Nyungan languages.

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Appendix 1: Reconstructions

1. Proto Western Karnic

Reconstructions with reflexes in Diyari (Di), Ngamini (Ng) and Yarluyandi (Yl) only.

- **tampu* ‘round’ Di, Ng, Yl: *dampu*
- **tanga*. ‘chase away’ Di, Ng, Yl: *danga*
- **tapa* ‘sore’ Di, Ng, Yl: *dapa*
- **tjtjithandrra* ‘star’ Di, Ng, Yl: *ditjithandrra*
- **kaka* ‘mother’s brother’ Di, Ng, Yl: *kaka*;
- **kangu* ‘sweat’ Di, Ng, Yl: *kangu*
- **karlka-* ‘wait for’ Di: *karlka-*; Ng: *karka-*; Yl: *karlka-*
- **kilpa* ‘cold’ Di: *kilpa*; Ng: *kirpa*; Yl: *kilpa*
- **kumarrhi* ‘blood’ Di, Ng, Yl: *kumarrhi*
- **kunankarri* ‘south’ Di, Ng: *kunankarri*; Yl: *kunan.garri*
- **kuru* ‘stealth’ Di, Ng, Yl: *kuru*
- **mani* ‘get’ Di, Ng, Yl: *mani*
- **marnathandrra* ‘tooth’ Di, Ng, Yl: *marnathandrra*
- **maru* ‘black’ Di, Ng, Yl: *maru*
- **miriwiri* ‘maggot’ Di, Ng, Yl: *miriwiri*
- **mulhaparra* ‘pigeon’ Di, Ng, Yl: *mulhaparra*
- **murruwa-* ‘scratch’ Di, Ng, Yl: *murrhuwa-*
- **nanda-* ‘hit’ Di: *nandrra-*; Ng: *dandrra-*; Yl: *nanta-* [also Thirrari *dandrra-*]
- **ngaka* ‘flow’ Di, Ng, Yl: *ngaka*
- **ngama-* ‘sit’ Di, Ng: *ngama-* Yl: *ngunhi-*
- **nganthi* ‘meat’ Di: *nganthi*; Ng, Yl: *ngantji*
- **ngayani* ‘1plincl nom’ Di: *ngayani*; Ng: *ngayini*; Yl: *ngayani*
- **ngayaninha* ‘1plinci acc’ Di: *ngayaninha*; Ng: *ngayininha*; Yl: *ngayaninha*
- **nguna* ‘arm’ Di, Ng, Yl: *nguna*
- **ngurrhamuku* ‘shin’ Di, Ng, Yl: *ngurrhamuku*
- **pakarna* ‘also’ Di, Ng, Yl: *pakarna*
- **pantu* ‘lake’ Di, Ng: *pantu*
- **pardaka-* ‘carry’ Di, Ng, Yl: *pardaka-*
- **parlka-* ‘travel’ Di: *parlka-*; Ng: *parka-* ‘run’; Yl: *parlka-*
- **parra* ‘hair’ Di, Ng, Yl: *parra*
- **patharra* ‘box tree’ Di, Ng, Yl: *patharra*
- **pira* ‘moon’ Di, Ng, Yl: *pira*
- **pjtj* ‘bark’ Di, Ng, Yl: *pitji*
- **putha* ‘shallow’ Di, Ng, Yl: *putha*
- **tharra* ‘thigh’ Di, Ng, Yl: *tharra*
- **wana* ‘yamstick’ Di, Ng: *wana*; Yl: *mangka*
- **wapa-* ‘go’ Di, Ng, Yl: *wapa-*
- **warda* ‘which’ Di, Ng, Yl: *warda*
- **warra-* ‘throw’ Di, Ng, Yl: *warra-*
- **wayi-* ‘cook’ Di, Ng: *wayi-*; Yl: *kula-*
- **wilha* ‘woman’ Di, Ng, Yl: *wilha*
- **wilhapirna* ‘old woman’ Di, Ng, Yl: *wilhapirna*
- **yantakarra* ‘west’ Di, Ng: *yantakarra*
- **yarrha* ‘that way’ Di: *yarrha* Ng, Yl: *yirrha*
- **yarrkj-* ‘bum’ Di, Ng, Yl: *yarrki-*
- **yika* ‘squeeze’ Di, Ng, Yl: *yika*

2. Proto Central Karnic

Reconstructions with reflexes in Diyari, Ngamini, Yarluyandi, Yandrruwandha (Ya), Yawarrawarrka (Yw), Mithaka (Mi), Karuwali (Ka).

- **taka* ‘to pierce’ Di: *daka-*; Ya: *drrika*
- **tama-* ‘to Cut’ Di, Ng, Yl: *dama-*; Ya, Yw: *drama-*
- **tampu* ‘testicles’ Ng, Yl, Ya, Mi: *dampu*
- **tanthu* ‘soft’ Di, Ya, YwR: *danthu*
- **tarla* ‘skin’ Di, Yl, Ya, Yw: *darla*; Ng: *karla*; Mi: *ngarla*; Ka: *karla*
- **tarnka-* ‘to find’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, YwR: *darnka-*
- **tarrpa-* ‘to sweep’ Di, YaR, YwR: *darrpa-*
- **tika-* ‘to name’ Di, Ng: *dika-*; Ya, YwR: *drrika-*
- **tinga-* ‘to rub, scrape’ Di, Ng: *dinga-*; Ya, YwR: *drringa-*
- **itji* ‘sun’ Di, Ng, Yl: *ditji*; Ya, Yw: *drritji*
- **itjipa-* ‘to dry in sun’ Di: *ditjipa-*; Ya *drritjipa-*
- **tuka-* ‘to take out’ Di: *dukara-*; Ya: *duka-*
- **tulyi-* ‘sprain’ Di, NgR: *dulyi-*; YaR, YwR: *drrulyi-*
- **turnka-* ‘to emerge’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya: *durnka-*
- **kaldi* ‘salty’ Di, Ng, Ya: *kaldri*; Yl: *kaldi*
- **kali* ‘already’ Ng, Yl, Ya: *kali*
- **kalka* ‘yesterday’ Ng, Yw: *kalka*; Di: *kalkawarrha*
- **kami* ‘father’s mother’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw: *kami*
- **kangi* ‘jester’ Di, NgR, Yak, YwR: *kangi*
- **kantha* ‘grass’ Di, NgR, Yl, Ya, YwR: *kantha*
- **kantu* ‘rock wallaby’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya: *kantu*
- **kaparrha* ‘root’ Di, Ng, YwR: *kaparrha*; Ya: *kaparrhi*
- **kaparrha* ‘come here!’ Ng, Yl, Ya: *kaparrha*
- **kapurrha* ‘armpit’ Di, Ng: *kapurrha*; Ya, Yw: *kapurrukutja*
- **kara* ‘might’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya: *kara*
- **kardi* ‘sister’s husband’ Di, NgR: *kardi*; Yak, YwR: *kardri*
- **karla* ‘empty’ Di, NgR, Yak, YwR: *karla*
- **karlipilhi* ‘butterfly’ Di, Ng, Ya, YwR: *karlipilhi*
- **karlku* ‘rushes’ Di, YaR, YwR: *karlku*
- **karri-* ‘to chase’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, YwR: *karri-*
- **karrtji-* ‘to turn’ Di, NgR, Yak, YwR: *karrtji-*
- **kawalka* ‘crow’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Mi: *kawalka*
- **kingka-* ‘to laugh’ Di, Ng, Yl: *kingka-*; Ya: *yingka-*; Mi: *kingki-*
- **kingkalyari-* ‘to overflow’ Di, NgR, YaR, YwR: *kingkalyari-*
- **karta* ‘boom’ Di, Yak, YwR: *karta*
- **kukunka* ‘kite hawk’ Di, Ng, Ya: *kukunka*
- **kirdakirda-* ‘to sigh’ Di, NgR, YaR, YwR: *kirdakirda-*
- **kuldrri* ‘top of spine’ Di, NgR, YaR, YwR: *kuldrri*
- **kuma* ‘bundle’ Di, NgR, YaR, YwR: *kuma*
- **kuma-* ‘to dance (of women)’ Di, YaR, YwR: *kuma-*; NgR: *kumu-*
- **kundrukundru* ‘cough’ Di, Ng, Ya, YwR: *kundrukundru*
- **kunampira* ‘wild tomato’ Di, NgR, Yak, YwR: *kunampira*
- **kungka-* ‘to limp’ Di, NgR, YwR: *kungka-*
- **kunmi* ‘haze’ Di, NgR, Yak, YwR: *kunmi*
- **kurli* ‘smell’ Di, NgR, YaR, YwR: *kurli*
- **kurlirka-* ‘to clean’ Di, NgR, YwR: *kurlirka-*
- **kurlkunga-* ‘to jump’ Di, Mi: *kurlkunga-*; Ng, Yl: *kurlkuma-*; Ya: *kurlkupa-*
- **kurluwa* ‘needlebush’ Di, NgR, Yak, YwR: *kurluwa*

*kurnpa- 'to caress' Di, YaR, YwR: *kurnpa-*; NgR: *kurnpu-*
 *kurnu 'one' Di, Ya, Yw, Mi: *kurnu*
 *kurra 'hoarse' Di, NgR, YaR, YwR: *kurra*
 *kurrhikira 'rainbow' Di, NgR, YaR, YwR: *kurrhikira*
 *kurritharrha- 'to forget' Di, NgR, YaR, YwR: *kurritharrha-*
 *kurrukurru 'secret' Di, NgR, YaR, YwR: *kurrukurru*
 *kutja 'eyelash, feather' Di, Ng, Yl, YaR, YwR: *kutja*
 *kuwu 'ignorant' Di, YaR, YwR: *kuwu*
 *malhantji 'bad' Di, Ya, Yw: *malhantji*
 *malkamalka 'striped' Di, Ng, Yak: *malkamalka*; Yw: *matjamatja*
 *malthi 'cool' Di, Ng, Yl, Mi: *malthi*; Ya: *malthi* "cold"
 *mama- 'to take back' Di, NgR, Yak, YwR: *mama-*
 *mankarrha 'girl' Di, Ng: *mankarrha*; Ya: *man.garrhi*; Yw: *man.garrha*
 *manu 'mind' Di, NgR, YaR, YwR: *manu*
 *maranguka- 'to help' Di, Yak, YwR: *maranguka-*; Ng: *maranguku-*
 *marankarrha 'spider' Di, Ng, Ya, YwR: *marankarrha*
 *marda 'stone' Di, Ng: *marda*; Yl: *marta*; Ya, Yw, Mi, Ka: *mardrra*
 *mardi 'heavy' Di, Ng: *mardi*; Ya: *mardrri*
 *mardu 'taste' Di, Ng, Ya, Yw: *mardu*
 *marlka 'mulga tree' Di, Ya: *marlka*
 *marna 'mouth' Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw: *marna*
 *marndikila 'wave' Di, NgR, YaR, YwR: *marndikila*
 *marnka 'steady' Di, YaR, YwR: *marnka*
 *marrha 'new' Di, NgR, Yak, YwR: *marrha*
 *marrhu 'wide' Di, Ng, YwR: *marrhu*
 *marrrka 'camping out' Di, NgR, YaR, YwR: *marrrka*
 *marrka 'to crawl' Di, Ng, Yl, Ya: *marrka*
 *marrrtji- 'to scream' Di, NgR, YwR: *marrrtji-*
 *matha- 'to bite' Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw, Mi: *matha-*
 *mawa 'hunger' Di, Ya, Yw: *mawa*; Ng, Yl: *muwa*; Mi: *mangka wapi*
 *milamila 'mirage' Di, NgR, YaR, YwR: *milamila*
 *milki 'eye' Di, Yl, Mi, Ka: *milki*; Ng: *mirki*; Ya, Yw: *mitji*
 *mjntji- 'to shine' Di, YaR, YwR: *mintji-*
 *multhipa- 'to sprinkle' Di, NgR, YaR, YwR: *multhipa-*
 *muntju 'fly' Ya, Yw: *mundju*; Di, Ng, Yl: *muntju*
 *mungara 'soul' Di, NgR, YaR, YwR: *mungara*
 *muntha 'self' Di, NgR, YaR, YwR: *muntha*
 *murrku 'muddy' Di, NgR, YaR, YwR: *murrku*
 *muya 'dry' Di, Ng, Yw: *muya*
 *ngakarni 'lsg dat/purp' Di, Ng, Yl, Ya: *ngakarni*
 *ngampu 'almost' Di, Ng, Yw: *ngampu*
 *ngamurrhu 'orphan' Di, NgR, YaR, YwR: *ngamurrhu*
 *ngana 'to be' Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, YwR: *ngana*
 *ngapaka- 'to make' Ng: *nganaka-*; Di, Yl: *nganka-*; Ya: *ngana-*
 *ngandi 'mother' Yl: *ngandi*; Di, Ng, Ya, Yw: *ngandrri*; Ka: *nganditja*
 *ngapu 'quiet' Di, Ng, Ya: *ngapu*
 *ngara 'heart' Di, Ng, Yl, Yw: *ngara*
 *ngarda then' Di, NgR: *ngarda*; YaR, YwR: *ngardrra*
 *ngari- 'to go down' Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Mi: *ngari-*
 *ngaru 'echo' Di, NgR, YaR, YwR: *ngaru*
 *ngatharra 'younger sibling' Ng, Yl, Mi, Ka: *ngatharra*; Ya, Yw: *ngatharri*; Di: *ngathata*

**ngatji*- ‘to beg’ Di, NgR, YaR, YwR: *ngatji*
**nhaka* ‘there’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya: *nhaka*
**nharrha*- ‘to drive away’ Di, NgR, YaR, YwR: *nharrha*-
**nharri* ‘dead’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Mi: *nharri*
**nhintha* ‘shame’ Ya: *ninda*; Di, Ng, Yl: *nhintha*
**nhingki* ‘here’ Ya: *nhinggi*; Di: *nhingki*
**nhuyu* ‘elder brother’ Ng, Yl, Mi, Ka: *nhuyu*; Di: *nhiyi*
**palha* ‘ground’ Yl, Ya, Yw, Mi, Ka: *palha*
**palthu* ‘road’ Di, Ya: *palthu*
**pandrra* ‘cooked’ Di, Ng, Ya: *pandrra*
**panga* ‘caterpillar’ Di, Ng, Ya: *panga*
**pangki* ‘rib’ Yw: *pangki*; Di, Ya: *pangkithirri*
**panthama*- ‘to smell’ Di, Ya, Yw: *panthama*-
**pantja* ‘knee’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw: *pantja*
**papa* ‘father’s sister’ Di, Ng, Yl, Mi: *papa*
**pariwilpa* ‘sky’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya: *pariwilpa*
**parlku* ‘body, flesh’ Di, Yl, Ya: *parlku*; Ng: *parku*
**parlu* ‘naked’ Di, NgR, YaR, YwR: *parlu*
**parrha*- ‘to lie down’ Di, Ng, Yl, Yw: *parrha*-; Mi, Ka: *parrhi*-
**payirri* ‘long’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw, Mi: *payirri*
**pilda* ‘possum’ Yl: *pilda*; Di, Ng, Ya: *pildrra*
**pirna* ‘big’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw, Mi: *pirna*
**pirri* ‘fingernail’ Di, Ng, Ya, Yw: *pirri*; Yl, Mi: *nhirri*
**piti* ‘anus’ Di, Ng, Yl: *piti*; Ya: *pidrri*
**pulka*- ‘to blow’ Di, Yl, Ya: *pulka*-; Ng: *pulku*-
**punnga* ‘lung’ Di, Ya: *punnga*
**pununu* ‘itch’ Di, YaR, YwR: *pununu*
**purda* ‘unripe’ Di, Ng, Ya: *purda*
**purnka*- ‘to grow’ Di, Ng, Ya: *purnka*-
**purri*- ‘to stoop’ Di, Ng, Ya: *purri*-
**purri*- ‘to fall’ Di, Ng, Yl, Mi: *purri*-; Ya, Yw: *warlka*-
**purra* ‘conscience’ Di, YaR, YwR: *purra*
**puthurrhu* ‘dust’ Di, Yl, Ya: *puthurrhu*
**putju* ‘blind’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw, Mi: *putju*
**thani*- ‘to copulate’ Di, Yl, Ya: *thani*-; Ng: *thardi*-
**tharda*- ‘to push’ Di, Ng: *thardupa*-; Ya: *thadrra*-
**thardi* ‘thirst’ Di, Ng: *thardi*; Yl: *tharti*; Ya: *thardrri*
**tharlpa* ‘ear, leaf’ Di, Yl, Ya, Yw: *tharlpa*; Ng: *tharpa*
**tharrha*- ‘to fly’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya: *tharrha*-
**thayi*- ‘to eat’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw, Mi, Ka: *thayi*-
**thilthirri* ‘centipede’ Di, Ya: *thilthirri*; Ng: *thinthirri*
**thiltja* ‘sinew’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, YwR: *thiltja*
**thinthipirri* ‘elbow’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw: *thinthipirri*
**thirri* ‘to fight’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw: *thirri*
**thuka*- ‘to carry on back’ Di, Ng, Ya, YwR: *thuka*-
**thurintji* ‘marrow’ Di, Ng, YaR, YwR: *thurintji*
**tjili* ‘soakage’ Di, Ng, Ya: *tjili*
**tjukurrhu* ‘kangaroo’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw, Mi: *tjukurrhu*
**wakarrha* ‘nape’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ka: *wakarrha*; Ya: *purndamitji*; Yw: *purnda*
**warla* ‘nest’ Di, NgR, Ya, YwR: *warla*
**warta* ‘butt, trunk’ Di, Ya: *warta*; Ng: *kardi*

**wirrhi*- ‘to enter’ Di, Ng, Yl, Mi: *wirrhi*-; Ya: *windrri*-
 **wuldrri* ‘narrow’ Di, Ng, Ya: *wuldrri*
 **yapa* ‘afraid’ Di: *yapa*; Ng, Yl: *parnda*; Ya: *yaba*
 **yaka*- ‘to ask’ Ng, Ya: *yaka*-; Di: *yakalka*-; Yl: *yakapa*-
 **yarra* ‘this way’ Di, Ng, Yw: *yarra*
 **yartu* ‘sated’ Di, Ya: *yartu*
 **yinpa*- ‘to send’ Yl, Ya: *yinba*-; Di, Ng: *yinpa*-
 **yingki*- ‘to cry’ Yl, Mi: *yingki*-; Ya, Yw: *yingki*-
 **yupa*- ‘to annoy’ Di, NgR, YaR, YwR: *yupa*-
 **yurndayurnda* ‘tadpole’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya: *yurndayurnda*

3. Proto Karnic

Reconstructions with reflexes in Diyari, Ngamini, Yarluyandi, Yandrruwandha, Yawarrawarra, Mithaka, Karuwali, Wangkumarra (Wm), Pitta-Pitta (Pp).

**tarrha*- ‘to ignite’ Di, Ng: *darrha*-; Yl: *darrhaka*-; Pp: *tarrhi*- “boil”
 **kaku* ‘elder sister’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw, Mi, Ka, Pp: *kaku*
 **kalhu* ‘liver’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, MI: *kalhu*; Pp: *kalu*
 **kalta* ‘blue-tongue lizard’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Wm: *kalta*
 **kalumpa* ‘clover’ Wm: *kalumba*; Di, Pp: *kalumpa*
 **kanku* ‘boy’ Yl, Wm: *kan.gu*; Di, Ng: *kanku*
 **kanti* ‘spinifex wax’ Di, Ng: *kandrri*; Pp: *kanthi*
 **kanyini* ‘mother’s mother’ Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw, Mi, Pp: *kanyini*; Wm: *kanyidja*; Di: *kanhini*
 **kari* ‘river’ Di, Yl, Ya: *karirrhi*; Mi: *karitjurru*; Pp: *karitjurru* “waterhole”
 **karlathurrha* ‘wild turkey’ Di, Ng, Mi: *karlathurrha*; Wm, Pp: *kalathurra*
 **karna* ‘person’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw, Mi, Ka, Wm, Pp, *karna*
 **karrha*- ‘to tie’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, YwR, Pp: *karrha*-; Wm: *karrhi*-
 **karrhawara* ‘eaglehawk’ Di, Ng, Yl, Wm: *karrhawara*; Ya: *karrhawa*; Yw: *karrawa*
 **karrhukarrhu* ‘old man’ Ya, Yw, Mi, Ka, Wm: *karrhukarrhu*; Ng: *karrkarrhu*; Yl: *kakarrhu*
 **karrka*- ‘to call out’ Di, Ya, Pp: *karrka*-; Wm: *karrki*-
 **karrpa*- ‘to sew’ Di, Ng, Ya, YwR, Wm: *karrpa*-; Yl: *karrpa*- “tie up”
 **kata* ‘louse’ Di, Ng, Yl, Mi: *kata*; Pp: *kata* “tick”; Ya, YwR: *kadrra*
 **kathi* ‘meat’ Ya, Yw, Mi, Pp: *kathi*
 **kathi*- ‘to climb’ Di, Ng, Yl, Yw, Mi, Pp: *kathi*-
 **kila* ‘galah’ Di, Ng: *kilankila*; Mi: *kilanggi*; Wm: *kilambara*; Pp: *kilantji*
 **kimpa*, ‘raw’ Ng, Ya, Pp: *kimpa*
 **kintha* ‘shrimp’ Di, Ng, Ya: *kintha*; Pp: *kintharu*; Wm: *thintha*
 **kirra* ‘boomerang’ Di, Ng, Yl: *kirra*; Mi, Pp: *tjirra*; Yw: *tjarrha*; Ya: *yarrha*
 **kirrhi* ‘clever’ Di, Ng, Ya, YwR, Pp: *kirrhi*
 **kuku* ‘back’ Mi, Pp: *kuku*; Di, Yl: *thuku*
 **kuna* ‘faeces’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw, Mi, Ka, Wm, Pp: *kuna*
 **kungku* ‘head’ Yl, Mi, Ka: *kungku*; Ya, Yw: *kungka*; Wm: *kuka*
 **kunki* ‘doctor’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya: *kunki*; Wm: *kunki* “ghost”
 **kunthi* ‘mosquito’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, YwR, Mi, Ka, Pp: *kunthi*
 **kurntikurnti* ‘crooked’ Di, Ng, YwR, Wm: *kurndikurndi*; Pp: *kurntikurnti*; Ya: *kurdikurdi*
 **kurrha*- ‘to put down’ Di, Yl, Ya, Yw, Mi: *kurrha*-; Pp: *kurrhala*- “drop”; Ng: *kurrhu*-
 **kurri* ‘mussel’ Di, Ng, Yl: *kurri*; Pp: *kurritja*
 **kurrparu* ‘magpie’ Di, Ng, Pp: *kurrparu*
 **kuti* ‘swan’ Di, Ng, Yl, Pp: *kuti*; Ya: *kudrri*
 **kuyamarrha* ‘dogwood tree’ Wm, Pp: *kuyamarrha*; Di: *kuyamarrha* “stick”
 **maka*; **thurrhu* ‘fire’ Ya, Yw, Pp: *maka*; Di, Ng, Yl, Mi, Ka: *thurrhu*
 **makamaka* ‘hot’ Ng, Ya, Pp: *makamaka*
 **malka* ‘mark’ Di, Ng, Ya, Wm, Pp: *malka*; YwR *matja*

**mara* ‘hand’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw, Mi, Ka, Wm, Pp: *mara*
**marni* ‘fat’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw, Ka, Wm: *marni*
**matja* ‘long ago’ Ya, YwR, Wm: *matja*; Di: *matja* “already”
**mimi* ‘lip’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Wm: *mimi*
**minta*; **pirta* ‘navel’ Ya: *mindrra*; Wm: *mindrra* “man’s navel”, **pirnta* “woman’s navel”; Di, Ng: *pirda*
**mingka* ‘hole’ Ya, Mi: *mingga*; Di, Ng, Yl, Pp: *mingka*
**minha* ‘what’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw, Wm, Pp: *minha*
**mirrtja* ‘noise’ Di, Ng, Ya: *mirrtja*; Wm: *itja*
**muka* ‘sleep’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Mi: *muka*; Wm: *muga*
**muku* ‘bone’ Di, Yl, Ya, Yw, Wm: *muku*
**mulha* ‘nose’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw, Mi, Ka, Wm: *mulha*; Pp: *milya*
**murta-* ‘stop, finish’ Di, Ya, YwR: *murda-*; Ng: *murdu-*; Wm *muru-*
**murlu* ‘crab’ Di, Ng, Pp: *murlu*; Mi: *marlu*
**murna* ‘chest’ Ka, Wm, Pp: *murna*; Ya: *murnathitha*; Yw: *murnakaldrda*; Di, Ng, Yl: *murnampirrhi*
**murrhamurrhu* ‘rough’ Di, Pp *murrhumurrhu*; Wm *murrhu*
**ngalta* ‘1dlincl nom’ Di, Ya, Yw: *ngaldrda*; Wm: *ngala*; Ng, Yl: *ngalku*
**ngaltanha* ‘1dlincl acc’ Di, Yw: *ngaldranha*; Wm: *ngalanha*; Ya: *ngalunha*; Ng, Yl: *ngalkunha*
**ngaltangka* ‘1dlincl dat/purp’ Di, Yw: *ngaldrarni*; Ya: *ngalungga(ni)*; Wm: *ngalanga(ni)*; Ng: *ngalkungga*; Yl: *ngalkungga*
**ngali* ‘1dlexcl nom’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw, Ka, Wm, Pp: *ngali*
**ngalingka* ‘1dlexcl dat/purp’ Yl: *ngalingga*; Ya: *ngalingga(ni)*; Ng: *ngalingka*; Wm: *ngalinga(ni)*; Pp: *ngalinga*; Di, Yw: *ngalirni*
**ngalinha* ‘1dlexcl acc’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw, Wm, Pp: *ngalinha*
**ngaltja* ‘saliva’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw, Wm, Pp: *ngaltja*
**ngama* ‘breast’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw, Mi, Ka, Wm: *ngama*; Pp: *ngamanya*
**ngampurrhu* ‘yellow-belly fish’ Ng, Yl, Ya, Mi: *ngampurrhu*; Wm: *ngampurrha*
**ngana* ‘1plexcl nom’ Wm: *ngana*; Pp: *ngarna*; Ya, Yw: *ngani*; Di: *ngayana*; Ng, Yl: *nganyurru*
**nganangka* ‘1plexcl dat/purp’ Wm: *ngananga(ni)*; Pp: *ngarnanga*; Ya: *nganingga(ni)*; Yw: *ngananga*; Ng: *nganyurrungka*; Yl: *nganyurrungga*; Di: *ngayanarni*
**ngananh* ‘1plexcl acc’ Wm: *ngananha*; Pp: *ngarnanha*; Ya, Yw: *nganinha*; Di: *ngayananha*; Ng, Yl: *nganyurrunha*
**ngantja-*; **yura-* ‘to want’ Di, Ng: *ngantja-*; Wm: *ngandja-*; Yl, Ya: *yura-*; Mi: *yuri-*
**nganta* ‘1plincl nom’ Ya, Yw, Wm: *ngandrra*
**ngantangka* ‘1plincl dat/purp’ Wm: *ngandrranga(ni)*; Yw: *ngandrrarni*; Ya: *nganungga(ni)*
**ngantanha* ‘1plincl acc’ Yw, Wm: *ngandrranha*; Ya: *nganunha*
**nganha* ‘lsg acc’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw, Mi, Wm: *nganha*; Pp: *nganya*
**nganyi* ‘lsg nom’ Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw, Mi, Ka, Wm: *nganyi*; Di: *nganhi*; Pp: *ngantja*
**ngapa* ‘water’ Di, Ng, Ya, Yw, Mi, Ka: *ngapa*; Pp: *ngapu*
**ngapiri* ‘father’ Di, Yl, Ya, Mi, Ka: *ngapiri*; Ng: *ngarpi*; Pp: *yapiri*
**ngara-*; **pangka-* ‘to hear’ Di, Ng, Ya, Wm: *ngara-*; Yl: *pangga-*; Yw: *panga-*; Pp: *pangka*; Mi, Ka: *pangki-*
**ngarta* ‘mother’s father’ Di, Ng, Yl: *ngardarda*; Yw: *ngardrra*; Mi: *ngarta*; Pp: *ngartarta* “father’s father”
**ngartu* ‘nardo’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya: *ngardu*; Pp: *ngartu*
**ngarnka* ‘beard’ Yl, Ya: *ngarn.ga*; Di, Ng, Ka: *ngarnka*; Wm, Pp: *nganka*
**ngarrhimatha* ‘flood’ Di: *ngarrhimatha*; Wm: *ngarimatha*; Pp: *ngarrhimantha*; Ng, Yl: *ngarrhumatha*
**ngatha* ‘child (father speaking)’ Di: *ngathamurrha*; Yl: *ngathapalki*; Ya: *ngathalki*; Pp: *ngathapiyaka*

**ngathani* ‘child (mother speaking)’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw: *ngathani*; Pp: *ngathari*
**ngathu* ‘1sg erg’ Di, Ya, Yw, Mi, Ka, Wm, Pp: *ngathu*; Ng, Yl: *ngathi*
**ngunku* ‘chewing tobacco’ Di, Ng, Wm, Pp: *ngunku*
**nguntji-* ‘to give’ Pp: *nguntji-*; Wm: *ngutja-*; Ya, Yw: *ngunyi-*
**ngurlu* ‘forehead’ Di, Ng, Yw, Wm, Pp: *ngurlu*
**ngurra* ‘camp’ Di, Ng, Ya, Yw, Ka, Wm, Pp: *ngurra*
**nhampa-* ‘to bury’ Yl, Mi, Wm: *nhampa-*; Ya, Yw: *nhamba-*
**nhantu* ‘3sgfem erg’ Ng, Yl: *nhandu*; Di, Ya, Yw: *nhandrru*; Wm: *nhandrra*; Pp: *nhantu*
**nhangkarni* ‘3sgfem datlpurp’ Di, Ng, Yl: *nhangkarni*; Ya: *nhanggani*; Wm: *nhangka(ni)*; Pp: *nhankari*
**nhanha* ‘3sgfem acc’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw, Wm: *nhanha*; Pp: *nhana*
**nhani* ‘3sgfem nom’ Di, Ya, Yw, Ka, Wm: *nhani*; Ng, Yl, Pp: *nhanpa*
**nhawu* ‘3sgmasc nom’ Di, Ka: *nhawu*; Ng, Yl: *nhapa*; Ya, Yw: *nhunu*; Pp: *nhuwa*; Wm: *nhiya*
**nhinha* ‘3sgmasc acc’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ka, Wm: *nhinha*; Ya, Yw, Pp: *yinha*
**nhulu* ‘3sgmasc erg’ Di, Ya, Yw, Wm, Pp: *nhulu*; Ng, Yl: *nhulpa*
**nhungkarni* ‘3sgmasc dat/purp’ Di, Ng, Yl: *nhungkarni*; Wm: *nhungka(ni)*; Ya: *nhunggani*; Yw: *nhungkunu*; Ka: *nhukarni*; Pp: *nhukari*
**nhupa* ‘spouse’ Wm: *nubadja*; Ya: *nhipa*; Di: *nhuwa*; Ng, Yl, Mi, Ka: *nhiwa*
**nyangi* ‘moon’ Ya, Yw, Mi, Pp: *nyangi*
**paku-* ‘to dig’ Di, Ya, Yw: *paku-*; Pp: *paka-*
**pali-* ‘to die’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ka: *pali-*; Wm: *palu-*; Ya: *paldrri-*
**palka-* ‘to split’ Di, Ng, Pp: *palka-*
**pampu* ‘egg’ Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw, Mi, Ka, Pp: *pampu*
**pani* ‘none’ Di, Ya: *pani*; Pp: *pani* ‘cannot’
**pangka-*; **ngara-* ‘to hear’ Yl: *pangga-*; Yw: *panga-*; Pp: *pangka-*; Mi, Ka: *pangki-*; Di, Ng, Ya, Wm: *ngara-*
**paratji* ‘light’ Di, Ng, Ka: *paratji*; Pp: *paratji* ‘flame’
**parta-* ‘to hold’ Di, Ng: *parda-*; Yl, Pp: *parta-*; Ya, Mi, Ka: *pardrra-*
**parnti-* ‘to hit’ Yl: *parndi-*; Ya, Yw, Mi, Wm: *parndrri-*
**parra* ‘stupid, mad’ Di: *parrhawara*; Wm: *parra*; Pp: *parrawangku*
**parrkulu* ‘two’ Yl, Ya, Yw, Mi, Ka, Wm: *parrkulu*; Di: *parrkulu* ‘three’; Pp: *parrkula*; Ng: *parrkuna*
**parru* ‘yellow ochre’ Di, Ng, Ya, YwR, Pp: *parru*
**parta* **pulyurrhu* ‘mud’ Ng, Yl, Mi, Pp: *parta*; Di, Ya: *pulyurrhu*; Wm: *pulyurrha*
**paya* ‘bird’ Di, Ng, Yl, Mi, Pp: *paya*
**pilpa* ‘eyebrow’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya: *pilpa*; YwR *pitpa*; Pp: *pilpa* ‘forehead’
**pinti* ‘grasshopper’ Di, Ng: *pindrri*; Wm: *pindrriya*; Pp: *pintilya*
**pirta*; **minta* ‘navel’ Di, Ng: *pirda*; Wm: *pirnta* ‘woman’s navel’, *mindrra* ‘man’s navel’; Ya: *mindrra*
**pirli* ‘dilly bag, net’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, YwR, Wm: *pirli*
**pitjirri* ‘pitchere’ Di, Ng, Pp: *pitjirri*; Wm: *pitjiri*
**pula* ‘3d! nom’ Di, Ya, Yw, Wm, Pp: *pula*; Ng, Yl: *pulku*
**pulangka* ‘3dl dat/purp’ Yw: *pulanggu*; Wm: *pulangani*; Pp: *pulanga*; Di: *pularni*; Ng: *pulkungka*; Yl: *pulkungga*; Ya: *pulgani*
**pulanha* ‘3d! acc’ Di, Wm, Pp: *pulanha*; Ya, Yw: *pulhu*; Ng, Yl: *pulkunha*
**pulyurrhu*; **parta* ‘mud’ Di, Ya: *pulyurrhu*; Wm: *pulyurrha*; Ng, Yl, Mi, Pp: *parta*
**purra* ‘urine’ Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw, Mi, Pp: *purra*; Wm: *yura*
**purrhalku* ‘brolga’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Mi, Pp: *purrhalku*
**thaka* ‘clay’ Di, Ng, Ya: *thaka*; Wm: *thaka* ‘ground’; Pp: *thakarra* ‘plain’
**thampangarra* ‘pelican’ Di, Ng, Pp: *thampangarra*
**thana* ‘3pl nom’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw, Wm, Pp: *thana*

**thanangka* ‘3pl dat/purp’ Yl: *thanangga*; Ng: *thanangka*; Pp: *thananga*; Wm: *thanangani*; Ya: *than.gani*; Yw: *than.ganu*; Di: *thanarni*
**thananha* ‘3pl acc’ Di, Ng, Yl, Wm, Pp: *thananha*; Ya, Yw: *thanha*
**thapa-* ‘to drink’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Mi: *thapa-*; Wm: *thapi-*
**tharli* ‘tongue’ Di, Ng, Yl, Mi, Pp: *tharli*
**tharrka-* ‘to stand’ Di, Ng, Yl, Mi, Pp: *tharrka*
**thika-* ‘to return’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Wm: *thika-*
**thina* ‘foot’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw, Mi, Ka, Wm, Pp: *thina*
**thinankarra*; **walpangkarrha* ‘north’ Di: *thinankarra*; Pp: *thinangarra*; Ya: *walpanggarrha*; Wm: *walpangarra*
**thintithinti* ‘willy wagtail’ Ng: *thindithindi*; Di, Ya, Mi, Wm: *thindrithindrri*
**thipi* ‘alive’ Di, Yl, Ya: *thipi*; Wm: *thiba*
**thirrihiwa* ‘east’ Di, Ng, Pp: *thirrihiwa*
**thuntu* ‘stomach’ Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw, Mi: *thundrru*; Pp: *tjurndu*
**thungka* ‘rotten’ Di, Ng, Yl, YaMi, Wm: *thungka*; Yw: *thungwa*
**thupu* ‘smoke’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw, Wm: *thupu*
**thurrhu*; **maka* ‘fire’ Di, Ng, Yl, Mi, Ka: *thurrhu*; Ya, Yw, PP: *maka*
**thurra* ‘ashes’ Ng, Ya, Yw, Wm: *thurra*
**tjimpa* ‘black’ Yw, Mi, Wm, Pp: *tjimpa*; Ya: *yimpa*
**wakuwaku* ‘cat fish’ Yl, Ya, Mi, Wm: *wakuwaku*
**walpangkarrha* **thinankarra* ‘north’ Ya: *walpanggarrha*; Wm: *walpangarra*; Di: *thinankarra*; Pp: *thinangarra*
**waltha-* ‘to bring’ Di, Ng, Ya, Wm: *waltha-*
**walya* ‘no’ Yl, Ya, Mi, Wm: *walya*; Yw: *watja*; Di, Ng: *wata*
**wama* ‘carpet snake’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Mi, Pp: *wama*
**wanthi-* ‘to search’ Di, Yl: *wanthi-*; Ya: *wandhi-*; Pp: *wantji-* ‘get up’
**wangka-* ‘to sing’ Di, Ng, Yl: *wangka-*; Pp: *wanka-*
**wani* ‘corroboree’ Di, Ng, Pp: *wani*
**wara* ‘who’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw, Wm, Pp: *wara*
**warnta* ‘short’ Ya, Wm: *warnta*; Di, Ng: *wardu*; Yl, Mi: *wartu*
**warrhukatji* ‘emu’ Mi: *warrhukatji*; Pp: *warrukatji*; Ng, Yl: *warrkatji*; Di: *warrhukathi*; Ya, Ka: *warruwidji*
**wintha* ‘when’ Di: *wintha*; Pp: *wintha* ‘where’; Ng: *wintja*
**wirlpa* ‘hole’ Di, Ya: *wirlpa*; Ng: *wirpa*; Pp: *wilpa* ‘sore, wound’; YwR *witpa*
**yantha-* ‘to speak’ Wm, Ya, Yw: *yandha-*; Di, Ng, Mi: *yatha-*; Yl: *yanhi-*
**yawarrha* ‘language’ Di, Ng, Yw, Wm: *yawarrha*; Ya: *yawarrhi*
**yingkarni* ‘2sg dat/purp’ Di, Ng, Yl: *yingkarni*; Ya, Yw: *yinggani*; Wm: *yinkani*; Pp: *yinkari*
**yina* ‘2sg acc’ Di, Ng, Yl: *yinanha*; Ya, Yw, Wm, Pp: *yina*
**yini* ‘2sg nom’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw, Mi, Ka, Wm: *yini*; Pp: *yinpa*
**yula* ‘2d1 nom’ Di, Ya, Yw, Wm: *yula*; Pp: *nhula*; Ng, Yl: *yulku*
**yulangka* ‘2d1 dat/purp’ Wm: *yulanga(ni)*; Di, Yw: *yularni*; Ya: *yulgani*; Ng: *yulkungka*; Yl: *yulkungga*; Pp: *nhulanga*
**yulanha* ‘2d1 acc’ Di, Wm: *yulanha*; Ng, Yl: *yulkunha*; Ya, Yw: *yulhu*; Pp: *nhulanha*
**yuntu* ‘2sg erg’ Di, Ya, Yw, Wm: *yundrru*; Ng, Yl: *yindi*; Ka: *yindu*; Pp: *yintu*
**yunka-* ‘sulky’ Di, Ya, Wm *yunka*; Pp *yunku-* ‘to sulk’
**yura-*; **ngantja-* ‘to want’ Yl, Ya, YwR: *yura-*; Mi: *yuri-*; Di, Ng: *ngantja-*; Wm: *ngandja-*
**yurlku* ‘throat’ Yl: *yurlku*; Mi: *yirku*; Pp: *yirka*; Ng: *yurku*
**yurlku-* ‘to swallow’ Di, Yl: *yurlka-*; Ng: *yurku-*; Ya: *yurru-*; Wm: *yurki-*
**yurra* ‘2pl nom’ Di, Ng, Yl, Ya, Yw, Wm: *yurra*; Pp: *nhurra*
**yurrangka* ‘2pl dat/purp’ Yl, Yw: *yurrangka*; Ng: *yurrangka*; Wm: *yurranga(ni)*; Di: *yurrarni*; Ya: *yun.gani*; Pp: *nhurranga*
**yurranha* ‘1pl acc’ Di, Ng, Yl, Wm: *yurranha*; Ya, Yw: *yunhu*; Pp: *nhurranha*

Appendix 2: Index of reconstructions

1dlexcl acc pK *ngalinha	also pWK *pakarna
1dlexcl dat/purp pK *ngalingka	annoy, to pCK *yupa-
1dlexcl nom pK *ngali	anus pCK *piti
1dlincl acc pK *ngaldanha	arm pWK *nguna
1dlincl dat/purp pK *ngaldangka	armpit pCK *kapurrha
1dlincl nom pK *ngalda	ashes pK *thurrpa
1pl acc pK *yurranha	ask, to pCK *yaka-
1plexcl acc pK *ngananha	back pK *kuku
1plexcl dat/purp pK *nganangka	back, to carry on pCK *thuka-
1plexcl nom pK *ngana	back, to take pCK *mama-
1plincl acc pWK *ngayaninha, pK *ngantanha	bad pCK *malhantji
1plincl dat/purp pK *ngantangka	bark pWK *pitji
1plincl nom pWK *ngayani, pK *nganta	be, to pCK *ngana-
1sg acc pK *nganha	beard pK *ngarnka
1sg dat/purp pCK *ngakarni	beg, to pCK *ngatji-
1sg erg pK *ngathu	big pCK *pirna
1sg nom pK *nganyi	bird pK *paya
2dl acc pK *yulanha	bite, to pCK *matha-
2dl dat/purp pK *yulangka	black pWK *maru, pK *tjimpa
2dl nom pK *yula	blind pCK *putju
2pl dat/purp pK *yurranka	blood pWK *kumarrhi
2pl nom pK *yurra	blow, to pCK *pulku-
2sg acc pK *yina	blue-tongue lizard pK *kalta
2sg dat/purp pK *yingkarni	body pCK *parlku
2sg erg pK *yuntu	bone pK *muku
2sg nom pK *yini	boom pCK *karta
3dl acc pK *pulanha	boomerang pK *kirra
3dl dat/purp pK *pulangka	box tree pWK *patharra
3dl nom pK *pula	boy pK *kanku
3pl acc pK *thananha	breast pK *ngama
3pl dat/purp pK *thanangka	bring, to pK *waltha-
3pl nom pK *thana	broilga pK *purrhalku
3sgfem acc pK *nhanha	brother, elder pCK *nhuyu
3sgfem dat/purp pK *nhangkarni	brother, mother's pWK *kaka
3sgfem erg pK *nhantu	bundle pCK *kuma
3sgfem nom pK *nhani	burn, to pWK *yarrki-
3sgmasc acc pK *nhinha	bury, to pK *nhampa-
3sgmasc dat/purp pK *nhungkarni	butt pCK *warta
3sgmasc erg pK *nhulu	butterfly pCK *karlipilhi
3sgmasc nom pK *nhawu	call, to pCK *tika-
afraid pCK *yaba	call out, to pK *karrka-
alive pK *thipi	camp pK *ngurra
almost pCK *ngampu	camping out pCK *marrka
already pCK *kali	caress, to pCK *kurnpa-
	carpet snake pK *wama

carry, to pWK **pardaka*-
 carry on back, to pCK **thuka*-
 cat fish pK **wakuwaku*
 caterpillar pCK **panga*
 centipede pCK **thilthirri*
 chase, to pCK **karri*-
 chase away, to pWK **tanga*- *
 chest pK **murna*
 chewing tobacco pK **ngunku*
 child (father's) pK **ngatha*
 child (mother's) pK **ngathani*
 clay pK **thaka*
 clean, to pCK **kurlirrk*a-
 clever pK **kirri*
 climb, to pK **kathi*-
 clover pK **kalumpa*
 cold pWK **kilpa*
 come here! pCK **kaparrha*
 conscience pCK **purrrka*
 cook, to pWK **wayi*-
 cooked pCK **pandrra*
 cool pCK **malthi*
 copulate, to pCK **thani*-
 corroboree pK **wani*
 cough pCK **kundrrukundrru*
 crab pK **murlu*
 crawl, to pCK **marrka*-
 crooked pK **kurntikurnti*
 crow pCK **kawalka*
 cry, to pCK **yungki*-
 cut, to pCK **tama*-
 dance (of women), to pCK **kuma*-
 dead pCK **nharri*
 die, to pK **pali*-
 dig, to pK **paku*-
 dilly bag pK **pirli*
 doctor pK **kunki*
 dogwood tree pK **kuyamarrha*
 down, to lie pCK **parrha*-
 down, to go pCK **ngari*-
 down, to put pK **kurrha*-
 drink, to pK **thapa*-
 drive away, to pCK **nharrha*-
 dry pCK **muya*
 dry in sun, to pCK **titjipa*-

dust pCK **puthurrhu*
 eaglehawk pK **karrhawara*
 ear pCK **tharlpa*
 east pK **thirriwa*
 eat, to pCK **thayi*-
 echo pCK **ngaru*
 egg pK **pampu*
 elbow pCK **thinthipirri*
 elder brother pCK **nhuyu*
 elder sister pK **kaku*
 emerge, to pCK **turnka*-
 empty pCK **karla*
 emu pK **warrhukatji*
 enter, to pCK **wirri*-
 eye pCK **milki*
 eyebrow pK **pilpa*
 eyelash pCK **kutja*
 faeces pK **kuna*
 fall, to pCK **purri*-
 fat pK **marni*
 father pK **ngapiri*
 father, mother's pK **ngarda*
 father's mother pCK **kami*
 father's sister pCK **papa*
 feather pCK **kutja*
 fight, to pCK **thirri*-
 find, to pCK **tarnka*-
 fingernail pCK **pirri*
 finish, to pK **murda*-
 fire pK **thurrhu*, **maka*
 fish, cat pK **wakuwaku*
 fish, yellow-belly pK **ngampurrh*
 flesh pCK **parlku*
 flood pK **ngarrhimatha*
 flow, to pWK **ngaka*-
 fly pCK **muntju*
 fly, to pCK **tharrha*-
 foot pK **thina*
 forehead pK **ngurlu*
 forget, to pCK **kurritharrha*-
 galah pK **kila(n)*
 get, to pWK **mani*-
 girl pCK **mankarrha*
 give, to pK **nguntji*-
 go, to pWK **wapa*-

go down, to pCK *ngari-
grass pCK *kantha
grasshopper pK *pinti
ground pCK *palha
grow, to pCK *purnka-
hair pWK *parra
hand pK *mara
hawk, kite pCK *kukunka
haze pCK *kunmi
head pK *kungku
hear, to pK *ngara-, *pangka-
heart pCK *ngara
heavy pCK *mardi
help, to pCK *maranguka-
here pCK *nhingi
hit, to pWK *nanda-
hit, to pK *parnti-
hoarse pCK *kurra
hold, to pK *parda-
hole pK *mingka
hole pK *wiripa
hot pK *makamaka
hunger pCK *mawa
husband, sister's pCK *kardi
ignite, to pK *tarrha-
ignorant pCK *kuwu
itch pCK *pununu
jester pCK *kangi
jump, to pCK *kurlunga-
kangaroo pCK *tjukurrhu
kite hawk pCK *kukunka
knee pCK *pantja
lake pWK *pantu
language pK *yawarra
laugh, to pCK *kingka-
leaf pCK *tharipa
lie down, to pCK *parrha-
light pK *paratji
limp, to pCK *kungka-
lip pK *mimi
liver pK *kalhu
lizard, blue-tongue pK *kalta
long pCK *payirrho
long ago pK *matja
louse pK *kata

lung pCK *punnga
mad pK *parrha
maggot pWK *miriwiri
magpie pK *kurrparu
make, to pCK *nganaka-
man, old pK *karrhukarrhu
mark pK *malka
marrow pCK *thurintji
meat pWK *nganthi, pK *kathi
might pCK *kara
mind pCK *manu
mirage pCK *milamila
moon pWK *pira, pK *nyangi
mosquito pK *kunthi
mother pCK *ngandi
mother, father's pCK *kami
mother, mother's pK *kanyini
mother's brother pWK *kaka
mother's father pK *ngarda
mother's mother pK *kanyini
mouth pCK *marna
mud pK *parta, *pulyurrhu
muddy pCK *murrku
mulga tree pCK *marlka
mussel pK *kurri
naked pCK *parlu
name, to pCK *tika-
nape pCK *wakarrha
nardoo pK *ngardu
narrow pCK *wuldrro
navel pK *pirda, *minta
needlebush pCK *kurluwa
nest pCK *warla
net pCK *pirli
new pCK *marrha
no pK *walya
noise pK *mirrtja
none pK *pani
north pK *thinankarra, *walpangkarrha
nose pK *mulha
ochre, yellow pK *parru
old man pK *karrhukarrhu
old woman pWK *wilhapirna
one pCK *kurnu
orphan pCK *ngamurrhu

out, to take pCK *tuka-
overflow, to pCK *kingkalyari-
pelican pK *thampangarra
person pK *karna
pierce, to pCK *taka-
pigeon pWK *mulhaparra
pinch, to pK *milka-
pitchere pK *pitjirrhi
possum pCK *pilda
push, to pCK *tharda-
put down, to pK *kurrha-
quiet pCK *ngapu
rainbow pCK *kurrhikira
raw pK *kimpa
return, to pK *thika-
rib pCK *pangki
river pK *karirrihi
road pCK *palthu
rock wallaby pCK *kantu
root pCK *kaparrha
rotten pK *thungka
rough pK *murrhumurrhu
round pWK *tampu
rub, to pCK *tinga-
rushes pCK *karlku
saliva pK *ngaltja
salty pCK *kaldi
sated pCK *yartu
scratch, to pWK *murruwa-
scream, to pCK *marrtji-
search, to pK *wanthi-
secret pCK *kurrukurru
self pCK *muntha
send, to pCK *yinpa-
sew, to pK *karrpa-
shallow pWK *putha
shame pCK *nhintha
shin pWK *ngurrhamuku
shine, to pCK *mintji-
short pK *warnta
shrimp pK *kintha
sibling, younger pCK *ngatharra
sigh, to pCK *kirdakirda-
sinew pCK *thiltja
sing, to pK *wangka-

sister, elder pK *kaku
sister, father's pCK *papa
sister's husband pCK *kardi
sit, to pWK *ngama-
skin pCK *tarla
sky pCK *pariwilpa
sleep pK *muka
smell, to pCK *panthama-
smell pCK *kurli
smoke pK *thupu
snake, carpet pK *wama
soakage pCK *tjili
soft pCK *tanthu
sore pWK *tapa
soul pCK *mungara
south pWK *kunankarri
speak, to pK *yantha-
spider pCK *marankarrha
spine, top of pCK *kuldrro
spinifex wax pK *kanti
split, to pK *palka-
spouse pK *nhupa
sprain pCK *tulyi-
sprinkle, to pCK *multhipa-
squeeze, to pWK *yika-
stand, to pK *tharrka-
star pWK *titjithandrra
steady pCK *marnka
stealth pWK *kuru
stomach pK *thuntu
stone pCK *marda
stoop, to pCK *purrihi-
stop, to pK *murda-
striped pCK *malkamalka
stupid pK *parrha
sulky pK *yunka
sun pCK *titji
sun, to dry in pCK *titjipa-
swallow, to pK *yurlika-
swan pK *kuti
sweat pWK *kangu
sweep, to pCK *tarrpa-
tadpole pCK *yurndayurnda
take back, to pCK *mama-
take out, to pCK *tuka-

taste pCK *mardu
testicles pCK *tampu
that way pWK *yarrha
then pCK *ngarda
there pCK *nhaka
thigh pWK *tharra
thirst pCK *thardi
this way pCK *yarra
throat pK *yurlku
throw, to pWK *warra-
tie, to pK *karrha-
tobacco, chewing pK *ngunku
tomato, wild pCK *kunampira
tongue pK *tharli
tooth pWK *marnathandrra
top of spine pCK *kuldrru
travel, to pWK *parlka-
tree, box pWK *patharra
tree, dogwood pK *kuyamarrha
tree, mulga pCK *marlka
trunk pCK *warta
turkey, wild pK *karlathurrha
tum, to pCK *karrtji-
two pK *parrkulu
unripe pCK *purda
urine pK *purra
wagtail, willy pK *thintithinti
wait for, to pWK *karlka-
wallaby, rock pCK *kantu
want, to pK *ngantja-, *yura-
water pK *ngapa
wave pCK *marndikila
wax, spinifex pK *kanti
west pWK *yantakarra
what pK *minha
when pK *wintha
which pWK *warda
whistle, to pK *wilpi-
who pK *wara
wide pCK *marrhu
wild tomato pCK *kunampira
wild turkey pK *karlathurrha
willy wagtail pK *thintithinti
woman pWK *wilha
woman, old pWK *wilhapirna

yamstick pWK *wana
yellow ochre pK *parru
yellow-belly fish pK *ngampurrhu
yesterday pCK *kalka
younger sibling pCK *ngatharra